

Machine learning discoveries of WNT10B-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Wnt family member 10B (WNT10B) is a cysteine-rich glycoprotein, that is a part of the WNT signaling pathway and is implicated in a range of cancers. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, WNT10B was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of WNT10B-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2nd order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which WNT10B-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of WNT10B with mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), GATA zinc finger containing domain antisense RNA (GATA-AS), fatty acid binding protein (FABP), helicase like transcription factor (HLTF), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA (LINC-xxxxx), frizzled class receptor (FZD), homeobox (HOX), cytochrome c oxidase assembly factor (COX), fibroblast growth factor (FGF), interleukin (IL), Rac GTPase (RAC), transforming growth factor beta (TGFB), low density lipoprotein receptor-related protein (LRP), notch receptor (NOTCH), SET and MYND domain containing (SMYD) and forkhead box (FOX) family.

Keywords: WNT10B, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning, Colorectal cancer.

1. Introduction

1.1. WNT10B

WNT10B has been found to be implicated in a range of cancers. In gastric cancer, the knockdown of WNT10B showed reduced expression of cell proliferation and migration

^{*}ML discoveries of WNT10B-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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¹Aspects of unpublished work were presented in a poster session at the first Wnt Gordon Research Conference, from 6-11 August 2017, held in Stowe, VT 05672, USA.

as well as inhibition of epithelial-mesenchymal transition Wu et al. [1]. On the other hand, WNT10B is also involved in the formation of bone mass and progenitor maintenance of various kinds of tissue, while deletion of the same leads to loss of bone mass and mesenchymal progenitor cells Stevens et al. [2]. Their contribution is also reported in axonal regeneration in injured CNS Tassew et al. [3]. Furthermore, like WNT10B, WNT10A and WNT6 have shown to play a major role in inhibiting adipogenesis and stimulates osteoblastogenesis while regulating the mesenchymal stem cells Cawthorn et al. [4] & Collins et al. [5]. Involvement in hepatocellular carcinoma of WNT10B has been found wherein it is shown that stable silencing of WNT10B leads to significant reduction in proliferation, colony formation, migration and invasion in HepG2 HCC cell line Wu et al. [6]. Its implication in breast cancer Wend et al. [7] & Chen et al. [8] as well as endometrial cancer Chen et al. [9] has also been reported.

In colorectal cancer, WNT10B has shown to play a dual function of both oncogenesis promotion via β -catenin/TCF pathway and the inhibition of cell growth, possibly via FGF family of proteins Yoshikawa et al. [10]. Methylation of WNT10B has been found in the some of the cancer cell lines while its reversal has lead to over-expression of the WNT10B. However, the over-expression of WNT10B has lead to reduced cell growth in cancer, indicating a β -catenin independent component to be behind such a phenomena. Methylation of over-expressed WNT10B and synergistic work with FGF family of proteins later indicate the promotion of oncogenesis, as has been demonstrated in Yoshikawa et al. [10]. WNT10B works in tandem with multiple components and some combinations of WNT10B have been confirmed in wet lab. However, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [11], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [12]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [13] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. WNT10B related synergies

2.1.1. WNT10B - MAPK15 / GATA6-AS1 / FABP5 / HLTf

Chen et al. [14] demonstrate that WNT10B provides defense mechanisms against doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity and apoptosis, via MAPK signaling. Khalid et al. [15] show that in GATA4 knockout mice bone marrow derived mesenchymal stem cells had reduction

in WNT ligands, particularly WNT10B as compared to control cells. They demonstrated that GATA4 is recruited to enhancers near WNT10B, thus regulating the WNT signalosome. In glioblastoma cells, Li et al. [16] exhibited a high level of FABP4 expression, and down-regulation of FABP4 suppressed tumor cell growth and metastasis. Further it was found that WNT10b, a regulator gene of FABP4, restored the effects of FABP4 down-regulation in glioblastoma cells. Helmer et al. [17] observe that HLTF regulates WNT10B signaling in brain. All these experimental validations point to existing combinatorial synergy between the involved members and WNT10B. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, individual family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these individual members along with WNT10B.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t WNT10B. HLTF - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1162 (linear) and 1137 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. Interestingly, MAPK15, GATA6-AS1 and FABP5 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMEBRS W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
MAPK15 - WNT10B	574	2470	2147
GATA6-AS1 - WNT10B	475	2031	2240
FABP5 - WNT10B	277	2222	2461
HLTF - WNT10B	1816	1162	1137

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • individual members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > HLTF.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t WNT10B	
HLTF	WNT10B

Table 2: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and individual members.

2.1.2. WNT10B - LINC-xxxxx

In colorectal cancer cells, Xi et al. [18] demonstrated that inhibition of LINC00261 caused an increase in microRNA-148a expression and a decrease in expression of WNT10B and β -catenin. These indicate that LINC00261 may affect colon cancer progression by modulating the miR-148a/WNT10b axis. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, LINC-xxxxx family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these LINC-xxxxx members along with WNT10B.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of LINC-xxxxx members w.r.t WNT10B. LINC00261 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 651 (laplace) and 1513 (rbf). LINC01123 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1126 (laplace) and 1528 (rbf). LINC00888 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1216 (laplace), 961 (linear) and 898 (rbf). LINC00338 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 530 (linear) and 543 (rbf). LINC00242 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 754 (linear) and 1001 (rbf). LINC00858 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 860 (linear) and 769 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, LINC01106 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING LINC-XXXXX FAMILY VS WNT10B							
RANKING OF LINC-XXXXX FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
LINC01106 - WNT10B	503	2295	1998	LINC00261 - WNT10B	651	1767	1513
LINC01123 - WNT10B	1126	1787	1528	LINC00888 - WNT10B	1216	961	898
LINC00338 - WNT10B	1651	530	543	LINC00242 - WNT10B	2258	754	1001
LINC00858 - WNT10B	2364	860	769				

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS LINC-xxxxx members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • LINC-xxxxx members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > LINC-00261 / 01123 / 00888 / 00338 / 00242 / 00858.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

LINC-xxxxx members w.r.t WNT10B

LINC-00261/01123/00888/00338/00242/00858 - WNT10B

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and LINC-xxxxx members.

2.1.3. WNT10B - FZD

In Tcell acute lymphoblastic leukemia, using MOLT4 and MUTZ-2 as leukemic cell models characterized by the expression of WNT10B^{IVS1}, Cassaro et al. [19] observed that WNT10B drives WNT activation via FZD6 receptor ligand binding. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, FZD family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FZD members along with WNT10B.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of FZD members w.r.t WNT10B. FZD7 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1121 (laplace), 1331 (linear) and 1395 (rbf). FZD3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 724 (linear) and 727 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING FZD FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF FZD FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FZD7 - WNT10B	1121	1331	1395
FZD3 - WNT10B	1805	724	727

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS FZD members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • FZD members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > FZD-7/3.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FZD members w.r.t WNT10B	
FZD-7/3 - WNT10B	

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and FZD members.

2.1.4. WNT10B - HOX

In oral squamous cell carcinoma cells, Dai et al. [20] found an enhanced migration ability induced by WNT10B, but it was reversed by HOXC10 knockdown. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, HOX family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these HOX members along with WNT10B.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of HOX members w.r.t WNT10B. HOXB8 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1233 (laplace), 1144 (linear) and 1487 (rbf). HOXB9 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1413 (laplace), 1264 (linear) and 1321 (rbf). HOXB4 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1554 (laplace), 1579 (linear) and 1354 (rbf). HOXA9 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1556 (laplace), 518 (linear) and 668 (rbf). HOXB5 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 296 (linear) and 481 (rbf). HOXA11 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 74 (linear) and 584 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HOXB13, HOXB7, HOXB3 and HOXA11-AS showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING HOX FAMILY VS WNT10B							
RANKING OF HOX FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
HOXB13 - WNT10B	82	2417	2583	HOXB7 - WNT10B	84	2709	2705
HOXB3 - WNT10B	838	1950	1912	HOXA11-AS - WNT10B	860	2021	1866
HOXB8 - WNT10B	1233	1144	1487	HOXB9 - WNT10B	1413	1264	1321
HOXB4 - WNT10B	1554	1579	1354	HOXA9 - WNT10B	1556	518	668
HOXB5 - WNT10B	1950	296	481	HOXA11 - WNT10B	2612	74	584

Table 7: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS HOX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • HOX members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B \rightarrow HOX-B8/B9/B4/A9/B5/A11.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

HOX members w.r.t WNT10B

HOX-B8/B9/B4/A9/B5/A11
WNT10B

Table 8: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and HOX members.

2.1.5. WNT10B - COX

WNT10B can promote bone morphogenetic protein 9 (BMP9) induced osteogenic differentiation via the COX2/p-CREB dependent manner, as observed by Liao et al. [21]. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, COX family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these COX members along with WNT10B.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9.

The table 9 shows rankings of COX members w.r.t WNT10B. COX10-AS1 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1429 (linear) and 1261 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, COX10, COX14 and COX18 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING COX FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF COX FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
COX10 - WNT10B	13	2300	2219
COX14 - WNT10B	448	2178	2186
COX18 - WNT10B	611	2224	2135
COX10-AS1 - WNT10B	1757	1429	1261

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS COX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - • COX members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > COX10-AS1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
COX members w.r.t WNT10B	
COX-10-AS1	WNT10B

Table 10: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and COX members.

2.1.6. WNT10B - FGF

Xiao et al. [22] support the hypothesis that the impaired anabolic response to parathyroid hormone in the absence of endogenous FGF2 is due in part to attenuated WNT signaling. WNT10B expression was altered by FGF2 deficiency. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, FGF family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FGF members along with WNT10B.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11.

The table 11 shows rankings of FGF members w.r.t WNT10B. FGF2 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1020 (laplace), 1223 (linear) and 1155 (rbf). FGFBP3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 740 (linear) and 384 (rbf). FGFR4 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 454 (linear) and 716 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING FGF FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF FGF FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FGF2 - WNT10B	1020	1223	1155
FGFBP3 - WNT10B	2353	740	384
FGFR4 - WNT10B	2403	454	716

Table 11: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS FGF members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • FGF members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > FGF-2/BP3/R4.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FGF members w.r.t WNT10B	
FGF-2/BP3/R4	WNT10B

Table 12: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and FGF members.

2.1.7. WNT10B - IL

He et al. [23] observed high level of IL17A promoted mesenchymal stem cells-2 polarization through WNT10B/RUNX2 pathway in new bone formation developed in ankylosing spondylitis. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, IL family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these IL members along with WNT10B.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of IL members w.r.t WNT10B. IL1RL2 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 991 (laplace) and 1502 (rbf). IL17D - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1546 (laplace), 762 (linear) and 706 (rbf). IL17RB - WNT10B shows low ranking of 825 (linear) and 573 (rbf). ILF3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 343 (linear) and 412

(rbf). ILF3-AS1 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 591 (linear) and 631 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, IL17RD, ILF2 and IL33 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING IL FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
IL17RD - WNT10B	330	2190	2407
ILF2 - WNT10B	529	2509	2338
IL1RL2 - WNT10B	991	1871	1502
IL33 - WNT10B	1118	1562	1694
IL17D - WNT10B	1546	762	706
IL17RB - WNT10B	1829	825	573
ILF3 - WNT10B	2231	343	412
ILF3-AS1 - WNT10B	2629	591	631

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS IL members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - • IL members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B - > IL-1RL2/17D/17RB/F3/F3-AS1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
IL members w.r.t WNT10B	
IL-1RL2/17D/17RB/F3/F3-AS1	WNT10B

Table 14: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and IL members.

2.1.8. WNT10B - RAC

Lee and Heur [24] observe that as WNT ligands regulate many critical cellular func-

tions, such as proliferation, they might be attractive candidates for modulation in human corneal endothelial dysfunction. The author's show that WNT10B causes nuclear transport and binding of RAC1 and β -catenin in human corneal endothelial cells, leading to the activation of cyclin D1 expression and proliferation. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, RAC family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these RAC members along with WNT10B.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of RAC members w.r.t WNT10B. RAC3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1419 (linear) and 1349 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, RACGAP1 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING RAC FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF RAC FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
RAC3 - WNT10B	1682	1419	1349
RACGAP1 - WNT10B	586	2072	1851

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS RAC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - • RAC members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B \rightarrow RAC-3.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
RAC members w.r.t WNT10B	
RAC-3	WNT10B

Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and RAC members.

2.1.9. WNT10B - TGFB

Ota et al. [25] have documented that osteoclasts secrete a homolog of Drosophila WNT10B, bone morphogenetic protein 6 (BMP6), and the chemokine sphingosin 1 phosphate (S1P) to promote mesenchymal cell mineralization in vitro. During bone re-

sorption, TGF β 1 is released from the bone extracellular matrix and activated by osteoclasts which increased osteoclast production of WNT10B, but not BMP6 or S1P. These results demonstrated that TGF β 1 stimulates WNT10B production in osteoclasts thus augment restoration of the bone lost during the resorptive phase of bone turnover. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, TGFB family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these TGFB members along with WNT10B.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of TGFB members w.r.t WNT10B. TGFB-R3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1539 (laplace), 1228 (linear) and 1270 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, TGFB-RAP1 and TGFB1 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING TGFB FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF TGFB FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
TGFB-RAP1 - WNT10B	682	2077	2106
TGFB1 - WNT10B	1514	1978	1905
TGFB-R3 - WNT10B	1539	1228	1270

Table 17: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS TGFB members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following influences - • TGFB members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > TGFB-R3.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
TGFB members w.r.t WNT10B	
TGFB-R3	WNT10B

Table 18: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and TGFB members.

2.1.10. WNT10B - LRP

Goel et al. [26] show that adult mammary ductal stem cell activity is maintained by

canonical WNT signal which requires both LRP5 and LRP6. The canonical ligands WNT9B and WNT10B are expressed in mammary gland. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, LRP family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these LRP members along with WNT10B.

Table 19 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 20 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 19. The table 19 shows rankings of LRP members w.r.t WNT10B. LRP3 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 895 (linear) and 1141 (rbf). LRP8 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 515 (linear) and 362 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING LRP FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF LRP FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
LRP3 - WNT10B	1680	895	1141
LRP8 - WNT10B	2252	515	362

Table 19: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS LRP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 19 graphically, with the following influences - • LRP members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > LRP-3/8.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
LRP members w.r.t WNT10B	
LRP-3/8	WNT10B

Table 20: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and LRP members.

2.1.11. WNT10B - NOTCH

In human U2OS osteosarcoma cells, Mödder et al. [27] demonstrated that WNT10B stimulated the NFκB and NOTCH pathways, which play important role in bone biology. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, NOTCH family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these NOTCH members along with WNT10B.

Table 21 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 22 generated from analysis of the ranks in table

21. The table 21 shows rankings of NOTCH members w.r.t WNT10B. NOTCH4 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 1223 (laplace) and 1104 (rbf). NOTCH1 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 308 (linear) and 388 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING NOTCH FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF NOTCH FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
NOTCH4 - WNT10B	1223	1631	1104
NOTCH1 - WNT10B	1711	308	388

Table 21: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS NOTCH members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 21 graphically, with the following influences - • NOTCH members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > NOTCH-4/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
NOTCH members w.r.t WNT10B	
NOTCH-4/1	WNT10B

Table 22: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and NOTCH members.

2.1.12. WNT10B - SMYD

Luo et al. [28] showed that SMYD3 was found to encode a novel histone methyltransferase involved in human cancer cells and activate the transcription of oncogene WNT10B, in mouse embryo fibroblast NIH3T3 cell line. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, SMYD family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these SMYD members along with WNT10B.

Table 23 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 24 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 23. The table 23 shows rankings of SMYD members w.r.t WNT10B. SMYD5 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 985 (linear) and 1209 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, SMYD3 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

RANKING SMYD FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF SMYD FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
SMYD3 - WNT10B	1464	1859	1714
SMYD5 - WNT10B	1606	985	1209

Table 23: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS SMYD members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 23 graphically, with the following influences - • SMYD members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > SMYD-5.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
SMYD members w.r.t WNT10B	
SMYD-5	WNT10B

Table 24: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and SMYD members.

2.1.13. WNT10B - FOX

Gerin et al. [29] show that WNT10B is induced by FOX transcription factors but it appears that increased WNT signaling alone is not sufficient to explain the mechanism whereby FOX transcription factors repress adipogenesis. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, FOX family members and WNT10B, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these FOX members along with WNT10B.

Table 25 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 26 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 25. The table 25 shows rankings of FOX members w.r.t WNT10B. FOXM1 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 619 (laplace), 1494 (linear) and 1371 (rbf). FOXJ1 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 516 (linear) and 467 (rbf). FOXA2 - WNT10B shows low ranking of 30 (linear) and 43 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FOXD2-AS1 showed high ranking with WNT10B, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with WNT10B, before the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 25 graphically, with the following influences - • FOX members w.r.t WNT10B with WNT10B – > FOX-M1/J1/A2.

RANKING FOX FAMILY VS WNT10B			
RANKING OF FOX FAMILY W.R.T WNT10B			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FOXD2-AS1 - WNT10B	331	2246	2006
FOXM1 - WNT10B	619	1494	1371
FOXJ1 - WNT10B	1782	516	467
FOXA2 - WNT10B	2573	30	43

Table 25: 2nd order interaction ranking between WNT10B VS FOX members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
FOX members w.r.t WNT10B	
FOX-M1/J1/A2	WNT10B

Table 26: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between WNT10B and FOX members.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic WNT10B 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of WNT10B-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [30].

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